

Exploring the CLEWs Nexus for integrated policy planning: a Guatemala case study

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Executive Summary

Climate change has impacted the small country of Guatemala in recent years with a significant temperature increase in recent years. In 2015 the Paris Agreements were signed, where Guatemala committed to achieve the total reduction of greenhouse gas emissions in its energy matrix and to have a sustainable agriculture plan, since the country's economy relies largely on this activity. Because of this, using the CLEWs modelling framework, 3 different scenarios were evaluated: Baseline (BAU), NetZero (NTZ) from 2050 and the correct use of resources (RLP).

Guatemala's energy matrix relies mostly on a diversified line of renewable power plants spread over its small portion of land, the second scenario proposes a significant investment in technologies such as hydroelectric, solar energy and mainly geothermal, of which currently only 3.5% is used. Guatemala is a country rich in natural resources that can be used in the energy matrix and agriculture, the third scenario will focus on a sustainable plan where fossil fuels can be limited as much as possible within the energy and agricultural contexts.

Certainly, the model is not perfect, none of them are. There are many variables that were not considered and data that came from the Chilean data set. Basic data was used from the Chilean data, but country specific was used for energy, land, and water too.

Introduction

There are many ways to achieve a goal such as the country's decarbonization by 2050, a plan that certainly does not seem so complicated if the right decisions are made. Guatemala has opted for renewable energies to mitigate greenhouse gases and they are based on hydroelectric power. However, we can mention that the diversity of the energy matrix that characterizes the Guatemalan market can have significant improvements with a good capital investment in technologies such as geothermal and the possibility of isolated systems for wind and solar technologies.

Despite having a very large renewable energy potential (only 15% is harnessed), Guatemala faces many significant problems, mainly social. Misinformation and poor education have an impact on the larger hydroelectric projects. Although this is part of the basic needs of a developing country, it is important to mention it, since the goal is large and the resources exist, but are difficult to access.

Despite everything, Guatemala continues to aim high to reach the goal of a country without emissions by 2050 with all the solutions that can be proposed and models like this one to be able to have a better, conscious, truthful, and reliable decision making.

Methodology

Guatemala does not have its own Starter Data Kit (SDK), so in recent years SDKs from other countries with considerable similarities to the Guatemalan energy matrix have been used. In this case, the Chilean SDK was used to model Guatemala. The reference energy system was updated from the documents of the Ministry of Energy and Mines of Guatemala and compared with the scenarios created. CLEWs is a modelling framework for long-term analysis that involves not only the energy matrix, but also the land and water use of the country in question. This provides flexibility and control when trying to model the evolution of crops and the emissions they may generate, not to mention the use of water bodies and precipitation for irrigated and non-irrigated areas.

The modeller must manage all the data related to the areas mentioned above for the CLEWs model to give a favourable result or one in which a decision can be made. Three scenarios were evaluated to determine paths to a green future in Guatemala such as Baseline (BAU), NetZero (NTZ), and Resource Right Utilization (RLP).

- For the BAU scenario the model shows us our best path if things continue as they are, considering the existing technologies, their limitations, it determines that wind energy will have a positive impact on Guatemala's energy matrix in a few years.
- The NTZ scenario presents a viable option for the utilization of geothermal energy for the elimination of fossil fuels and reach a country without emissions in 2050. Of course, this entails a high investment since it is one of the least exploited technologies in the country.
- For the third and last scenario, the RLP proposes, not the complete elimination of fossil fuels, but their limitation in the national territory in all sectors, proposing hydroelectric technology as a strong contender to replace the energy supplied by diesel.

Scenario Label	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
Baseline (BAU)	Fossil fuels had 34.88% of Energy production.	Oil palm is taking the place of tropical forests at a rampant rate and gas emissions are not declining as they should be.
NetZero (NTZ)	Emissions in equilibrium in energy and agricultural sectors	The elimination of fossil fuels will help recapitalize investment for RES.
Resource Leverage (RLP)	Limits for fossil fuels, land, and water for better organization	Elimination of crops harmful to the fertile soil, use of water bodies and water treatment plants.

Figure 1. Summary of scenarios explored in the modelling explained above.

Results

Energy will never stop being demanded, this is what our models tell us and represents the progress that the model expects the country to make in the following years. Because of this, the model shows us for our first scenario a scenario with low diversity and high emissions, as is the BAU:

Figure 2. BAU Energy.

Figure 3. BAU Emissions.

There is also good news, agriculture will continue to be one of Guatemala's main economic activities and corn will continue to be important; however, the model opts for palm oil:

Figure 4. BAU Crop Production.

However, for our second scenario, where we propose the complete elimination of fossil fuels, we see a glimmer of hope in terms of energy diversity and the elimination of greenhouse gases. The model proposes a combination of hydroelectric plants, solar plants, and significant investment in the least exploited technology in Guatemala, geothermal energy:

Figure 5. NTZ Energy.

Emissions, as mentioned above, were practically eliminated in their entirety, so that, in this scenario, it is possible to reach 2050 without carbon emissions:

Figure 6. NTZ Emissions.

Since the country's energy matrix was almost entirely worked on and the use of this energy to replace the fossil fuels that prevailed in agriculture, land use and crop production followed a path very similar to the one we met in the BAU scenario.

Figure 7. NTZ Crop Production.

Since agriculture remained almost the same, the utilization of water bodies and the country's precipitation remained the same in this scenario.

Within the third scenario, we proposed the use of resources for a better organization of resources. In this scenario, we proposed a sufficiently large limitation for fossil fuels to mitigate the emissions they cause, especially in the energy sector:

Figure 8. RLP Energy.

Figure 8 shows the decrease of fuels such as coal, biomass, and fuel oil, which constituted a large part of the emissions generated by the energy sector.

Figure 9. RLP Emissions.

Although greenhouse gases were not eliminated 100%, they were significantly reduced, and this allows us to have a good use of the land, taking into consideration the damage that some crops can do to the soil where they are located. Such is the case of the palm that obtained a considerable decrease to give place to maize, which corresponds to one of the main crops in Guatemala, considering the diet that we have.

Figure 10. RLP Crop Production.

Discussion

Within the energy and farming contexts, the permanence of fossil fuels ends up being a threat to both scenarios. In both the NTZ and the RLP, emissions generated by fuels are reduced, in one more than in the other. Guatemala was very ambitious when it signed up to be one of the countries that would reach decarbonization of the energy sector by 2050. Our model presents a path on which we can get there, however, the capital investment exceeds the budget of the Ministry of Energy and Mines for upgrading technologies and updating plant equipment. Another path will have to be taken. Still, the other scenario proposes both, investment towards little exploited technologies such as geothermal, the existing and very strong hydroelectric and a curious increase in wind energy since the wind energy potential in Guatemala is not that high. Something I can emphasize is the correct use of water and a better distribution of land, decreasing the damage created by palm oil plantations and increasing the production of corn and coffee, which are quality products worldwide.

Conclusions

Guatemala is a country rich in natural resources that can be exploited in different ways, among which we can highlight the care of water, sustainable development through circular economy, responsible agriculture, and a well-diversified energy matrix, with distributed generation exploring new technologies that will lead us to decarbonization by 2050.

Agriculture is the main economic activity in Guatemala. Most crops are native to the country; however, there are some, such as African palm (from which palm oil is acquired), which cause damage to the tropical soil, leaving it infertile for several years before it can be used again for cultivation. Since Guatemala is an agricultural country with so little space, this is a luxury that cannot be afforded, so the mitigation of palm oil plantations can be achieved through a trade strategy that satisfies the economy that the oil can leave behind.

Water is life. Water makes the world what we know it to be today, and within the agricultural and energy sectors, water translates as profit. Therefore, its responsible use is of great importance in these contexts. Without leaving aside the public context, much of the contamination of the world's water bodies is due to plastics that humans have discarded. A law that promotes the correct use of water, its treatment in industrial plants and its responsible distribution would bring the water problems in Guatemala to a higher level of priority.

Thanks to the use of modeling tools, we can observe that, depending on the different known variables that we enter the model, it will tell us the best path to follow. It is essential to use the correct and real data for each country, so the DSK of Guatemala will be among my plans for future EMP-LACs.

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